

A mmWave RF-EMF exposure sensor for 5G FR2: concept and design

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SUMMARY

Next to frequency range 1 (FR1), which covers all frequency bands situated between 410 MHz and 7125 MHz, the fifth generation telecommunication (5G) also introduced the usage of frequency range 2 (FR2). FR2 stretches from 24.25 GHz to 71.0 GHz which is quite a jump in frequencies compared to the frequencies used for previously deployed technologies (2G, 3G, and 4G). The introduction of this frequency range requires the need for new measurement protocols and equipment to measure radio frequency electromagnetic field (RF-EMFs) exposure induced by 5G communication at these mmWave frequencies. For FR1, several low-cost and compact RF-EMF exposure sensors already exist and are deployed in large scale RF-EMF monitoring networks. But, the concept of the FR1 RF-EMF sensor cannot be replicated to achieve similar performances i.e. similar dynamic range, to monitor FR2 without “breaking the bank” – they are expensive. To realise an FR2 RF-EMF exposure sensor, a novel approach based on a mixer is proposed. Initial testing of the mixer was performed. The next steps of the prototype are also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of the fifth generation (5G) of telecommunications networks is to provide larger bandwidths and to support higher data rates compared to previously deployed technologies (2G, 3G, and 4G). To achieve these goals, new frequency bands were introduced. These frequency bands are classed into two frequency ranges: frequency range 1 (FR1) and frequency range 2 (FR2) [1,2]. FR1 stretches from 410 MHz to 7125 MHz and already includes traditional cellular traffic from previously deployed technologies. FR2 stretches from 24.25 GHz to 71.0 GHz which is quite a jump in frequencies compared to the frequencies used for older technologies. Five frequency bands (see Table 1) were defined within in FR2 which are going to be used for 5G communication. The introduction of the new frequency bands requires the need for new measurement protocols and equipment to measure radio frequency electromagnetic field (RF-EMFs) exposure induced by 5G communication at these mmWave frequencies. Goegebeur et al. [3] performed a measurement campaign near a 5G FR2 base station in Sweden. Goegebeur used a horn antenna (A-Info LJ-SB-180400-KF) and omnidirectional antenna (Mi-Wave 267 Series), which were connected to a spectrum and signal analyser (R&S®FSV3030) to measure the RF-EMF exposure. Although the setup is quite robust and can be used to perform reliable measurements, it is rather bulky and requires expensive equipment and licenses. Therefore, a different approach is required to perform less expensive and/or longer measurement campaigns.

For FR1, several low-cost and compact RF-EMF exposure sensors already exist [4,5] and are deployed in large scale RF-EMF monitoring networks [6]. Deprez et al. [4] introduced a modular RF-EMF exposure sensor capable to monitor four telecommunication technologies (GSM, UMTS, LTE, 5G) operating at different frequencies. The design consists of four dedicated RF front ends consisting of off-the-shelf band pass filters, low noise amplifiers (LNA), and power detectors. Often a root mean square (RMS) power detector is used. The output of the power detector is measured by an analog-to-digital converter (ADC). The concept of the FR1 RF-EMF exposure sensor is shown in Figure 1.

For FR2, a similar approach is possible, but the required components are expensive and/or similar performances (e.g. dynamic range) as the FR1 RF-EMF sensors are hard to achieve without breaking the bank. This paper suggests an adaptation of the concept to realise a RF-EMF exposure sensor suited to monitor the n258 frequency band. This band will potentially be used for 5G communication in Europe.

Table 1: Frequency bands used by 5G in FR2 [1,2]

Frequency band	Frequency range [GHz]
n257	26.5-29.5
n258	24.25-27.5
n259	39.5-43.5
n260	37.0-40.0
n261	27.5-28.35

Figure 1: FR1 RF-EMF exposure sensor concept ; The concept of the sensor consist of a band pass filter, a LNA, a RMS power detector and an ADC. A microcontroller (μC) is used to readout the data from the ADC, program the ADC, and to process the data.

METHODS

Concept

The current exposure sensor concept requires a power detector e.g., an RMS power detector, capable to measure the power of mmWave signals. The options are rather limited and the power detectors capable to measure mmWave signals do not deliver a large dynamic range of at least 50 dB (e.g. LTC5596 – dynamic range 35 dB) or are expensive (HMC662LP3ETR – price ~950 euro).

A large variety of power detectors, capable to measure the power of RF signals of sub 6 GHz frequency signals, is available. Therefore, the idea to “lower” the frequency of the original mmWave signal (24.25 GHz – 27.5 GHz) to sub 6 GHz frequencies is investigated. The carrier frequency of a signal can be changed, utilizing a frequency mixer. In this case, a lower frequency is preferred so a downconverter is required.

A downconverter converts a signal, denoted as RF to an intermediate frequency (IF) by “multiplying” the original signal with a signal generated by a local oscillator (LO). The frequency of the output signal is the sum or difference (or a combination of the sum of a multitude of the frequencies) of the frequencies of the RF and LO signal (Equation 1). The unwanted IF signals can be suppressed by adding extra filtering (e.g. a low pass filter) of the IF output of the mixer. The concept of this approach is shown in Figure 2.

$$f_{IF} = mf_{RF} \pm nf_{LO} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: FR2 RF-EMF exposure sensor concept ; The concept of the sensor consists of a band pass filter, LNA, mixer (downconverter), low pass filter, RMS power detector and a ADC. The downconverter is used to convert the RF signal to a lower (IF) frequency.

Application of the concept

The FR2 RF-EMF exposure sensor proposed in this paper utilises this approach. The decision was made to convert mmWave signals to baseband i.e., the frequency of the LO signal is the same as the lowest expected frequency of the RF signal. The filter used in the initial prototype (BFCQ-2602+) is suited to

for large part of the n258 frequency band. The insertion loss between 25 GHz and 27.5 GHz is 2.0 dB. Therefore, the chosen LO frequency was 25 GHz. As a result, the wanted IF frequencies are between DC and 2.5 GHz.

The possibility of using a wide variety of power detectors at the output of the mixer is not the only advantage of this approach. Some mixers, e.g. the one that is going to be used in the initial prototype also has a conversion gain x , i.e. the IF signal will be x dB higher as the power of the input signal. Which is beneficial for the noise floor of the total sensor. The noise floor of the sensor could be further reduced (or the dynamic range could be further increased) by adding an extra amplifier at the output of the downconverter i.e., between the low pass filter and the RMS detector.

The main disadvantage of this approach is the increase in complexity. More subblocks or components are needed. The mixer also has some limitations and therefore has requirements for the power level and frequency for the RF and LO signals. A key component of the sensor is the generation of a stable LO signal, which meets the requirements of the mixer.

First prototype

The choice was made to split the sensor into subblocks e.g., circuitry required to generate the LO signal. The subblocks are designed and tested separately. The design consists of two phases, first a component study is conducted. Next, a printed circuit board (PCB) is made to test the subblock and to verify the performance of the selected components. The following tests need to be performed.

- Verify the performance of the RF band pass filter.
- Test the capabilities of the mixer.
- Generate a stable LO signal and verify the output power.
- Low pass filter and power detector circuitry
- Digital circuitry to process the results.

RESULTS

Initial tests were conducted with the mixer. RF signals with frequencies between 25 GHz and 27.5 GHz were generated with a signal generator and injected in the RF port of the mixer. A second signal-generator was used to generate and inject the LO signal in the mixer. The output of the mixer was connected to a spectrum analyser. Figure 3 shows the results of one test case. A sine wave at frequency of 27.5 GHz and power of -70 dBm was injected in the RF port of the mixer. A 12 GHz signal with a power of 3 dBm was injected in the LO port of the mixer. The expected frequency of the signal at the output of the mixer (IF port) is 3.5 GHz. The power of the signal at this port is -57.58 dBm which translates to a conversion gain of 12.42 dB.

CONCLUSIONS

To realise an FR2 RF-EMF exposure sensor, a novel approach based on a mixer is proposed. The design is split into several parts and the mixer of the prototype was tested. The conversion gain of the mixer used during the first tests was 12.42 dB for f_{RF} of 27.5 GHz, f_{LO} of 12 GHz and P_{LO} of 3 dBm. The idea and concept for an FR2 RF-EMF exposure sensor is promising and a clear plan of action is suggested to achieve a first prototype to measure FR2 RF-EMF exposure with of-the-shelf components.

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Figure 3: Test of mixer, the power of the IF signal (in dBm) is shown on the y-axis, the frequency is shown on the x-axis ; The signal injected in the RF port of the mixer was a sine wave at a frequency of 27.5 GHz and power of -70 dBm. The signal injected at the LO port was a sine wave at a frequency of 12 GHz and power of 3 dBm. Resulting in a signal at the output of the IF port with a frequency of 3.5 GHz and power level of -57.58 dBm.

REFERENCES

- [1] 3GPP, “3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network; NR; User Equipment (UE) radio transmission and reception; Part 1: Range 1 Standalone (Release 18),” 3GPP, Tech. Rep. TS 38.101-1 V18.5.0 (2024-03), 2024.
- [2] R. Dilli, “Analysis of 5G wireless systems in FR1 and FR2 frequency bands,” in 2020 2nd International Conference on Innovative Mechanisms for Industry Applications (ICIMIA), 2020, pp. 767–772.
- [3] S. Goegebeur, K. Deprez, D. Colombi, J. E. Bischoff, C. Di Paola, B. Stroobandt, L. Verloock, S. Aerts, C. Törnevik, and W. Joseph, “A comparative study of in situ methodologies for assessment of RF EMF exposure from a 5G FR2 base station,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 132 552–132 564, 2024.
- [4] K. Deprez, L. Colussi, E. Korkmaz, S. Aerts, D. Land, S. Littel, L. Verloock, D. Plets, W. Joseph, and J. Bolte, “Comparison of low-cost 5G electromagnetic field sensors,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 6, p. 3312, Mar. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23063312>
- [5] J. Van der Straeten, H. Van Bladel, Kenneth Deprez, Sam Aerts, Günter Vermeeren, and Wout Joseph, “Design of a low-cost triaxial 5G RF-EMF exposure sensor,” in *BioEM 2024, Joint Annual Meeting of the Bioelectromagnetics Society and the European BioElectromagnetics Association*, Abstract collection, Chania, Greece, 2024.
- [6] C. Apostolidis, A. Manassas, S. Iakovidis, and T. Samaras, “Electromagnetic fields in the environment: An update of monitoring networks in Europe,” in 2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC), 2022, pp. 1–3.